

Strengthening Open Science in Synthetic Cell Research and Innovation

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Short title: Open science in synthetic cell research

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APPENDIX 1:

Nucleus Whitepaper

Nucleus – a developer ecosystem building synthetic cells (July 11, 2025)

Mastering the engineering of biology will unlock new modes of technology that enable humanity to flourish. Yet, the inherent complexity and diversity of natural cells means that the best we can do today is develop an increasing number of bespoke engineering tools and solutions. Engineering efforts are now organized as small teams that must own the entire development “stack”, from system design to DNA implementation, constraining progress to particular cellular systems with tens of engineered components that are rarely interoperable in new contexts. Making it easy to build integrated systems with hundreds to thousands of components will require new technical and social frameworks that move beyond natural systems and idiosyncratic engineering practices.

Nucleus is a platform for the collaborative development of synthetic cells—non-living, genetically-programmed biomolecular machines—that are entirely composed of well-understood, modular, components. Synthetic cells are the most promising vehicle for systematically integrating and deploying thousands of components at scale for diverse contexts and applications. Nucleus includes technical resources such as validated protocols, plasmids, and software code that allow engineers to focus on developing new capacities, rather than reinventing what has already been done. Nucleus is an open source project built on open science practices where everyone is encouraged and free to use, modify, and build upon shared capabilities. By providing an accessible and well-documented platform, Nucleus aims to be biology’s Arduino.

Nucleus stands to operationalize the hundreds of foundational components and capabilities that are actively being developed by the frontier synthetic cell community. These components are now largely developed in isolation, without shared design principles or common features (e.g., buffer conditions or membrane compositions), and thus are slow and difficult to combine and build upon. By developing components using the same underlying platform, integration and scale become possible. Nucleus provides a technical framework built on pre-existing optimization and validation of basic cell-building components (cytosol, container, and content) and reference functional cell designs. It also provides the underlying documentation and protocols to use these components, making it the most expedient means of creating baseline cells upon which to build new functionality.

Nucleus serves as the venue for the co-development, specification, and standardization of the means to build components, modules, and cells at increasing levels of sophistication. Collaboratively building and integrating at scale requires working in a way often at odds with the default means of working in academia. Nucleus includes data-sharing infrastructure that enables geographically distributed engineers to easily share and analyze datasets. This infrastructure includes integration with a publishing suite, enabling engineers to share ideas and results. Nucleus as a social framework acts to teach, incentivize, and build energy around rapid, open sharing to increase the velocity and scale of collaboration within the community.

b.next is the open core synthetic cell company based in San Francisco. b.next developed the Nucleus Ecosystem to support the development of a synthetic cell industry built on collaboration through open technology. As a company, it provides core services and reagents to deliver synthetic cell applications to the world. For example, the b.next Foundry is the manufacturing pipeline for producing key reagents, components, and physical development tools (e.g., Nucleus PURE, measurement standards, debugging kits, and DNA). b.next also hosts Nucleus Labs, the physical embodiment of the Nucleus Ecosystem, providing built-for-purpose laboratory space for developers from across institutions to perform integration.

Nucleus increases the capabilities of synthetic cells for all.

Nucleus consists of three core pillars that serve distinct functions. The Nucleus Distribution is an integrated knowledge base and collection of tools that enable the Developer Community to build with a shared foundation. Nucleus Hub is a collaboration platform that provides digital environments and tools that enable developers to work together. Nucleus Developer Notes (DevNotes) is a publishing platform for DevNotes, short-form scientific notes for rapidly communicating on-going work. DevNotes are how the developer community can contribute to the collaborative development of the Nucleus Distribution.

Developers start with the Nucleus Distribution; build with Nucleus Hub; and share progress and results with DevNotes. New capacities are validated and integrated back into the Nucleus Distribution for use by the Developer Community (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Overview of the Nucleus Ecosystem. Boxes represent distinct pillars of the Nucleus Ecosystem and arrows show the flow of information between them.

1 - Nucleus Distribution (nucleus.bnext.bio)

The Nucleus Distribution is an open-source collection of protocols, designs, datasets, software code, and biological materials that are designed for interoperability. The Developer Community

collaborates to develop the Nucleus Distribution. The distribution supports PURE-based modules and synthetic cells. The Distribution is versioned and updated quarterly based on community contributions and integration work done by the Core Development Team at b.next. The key elements of the Distribution include:

- **Nucleus DNA Distribution.** The Nucleus DNA Distribution consists of genetic constructs that can be used to engineer synthetic cells. It contains plasmid DNA for making the PURE system, fluorescent reporter proteins, and a growing set of genetically encoded modules that expand the functionality and improve the performance of the underlying PURE system such as molecular logic, increased metabolism, and membrane-associated proteins. The constructs have been experimentally validated and datasets describing expected behavior are provided. The genetic constructs are open source (sequence information available on [GitHub](#)) and open access (available under [OpenMTA](#)). The Distribution is currently available by sending a request to build@bnext.bio.
- **Nucleus Protocols.** Nucleus Protocols are validated protocols that describe how to use the Nucleus DNA Distribution to make a variety of cytosols and synthetic cells based on the PURE system. They include detailed lists of materials and reagents and provide step-by-step instructions that can be used directly at the lab bench.
- **Cell Development Kit (CDK).** The CDK provides supporting software code to work effectively with cells and cell components. At present, this particularly includes tools for standardized measurement of cytosol (plate reader) and cell (microscopy) data. Collection and analysis of such data in a way that is quantitatively comparable and shareable between collaborating laboratories is critical for co-development, integration, and to enable later uses of the data such as modeling or replication of a cell design. The CDK increasingly includes the means for specification of cell designs and automation of cell-building processes, and the CDK forms the first step of the process to share designs, experiments, data, and analysis by various means (GitHub, Nucleus Hub, Developer Notes, etc.).

2 - Nucleus Hub (hub.nucleus.engineering)

The Nucleus Hub is a shared environment pre-loaded with digital tools, such as the CDK and DevNote publishing suite, that helps facilitate collaboration between members of the ecosystem. Nucleus Hub is based on Jupyter Hub and obviates the need for users to manage complicated software environments. As such, it provides a way for developers to share and analyze data in the cloud using a common set of standard tools. Nucleus Hub is configured to accommodate expanding circles of trust. Developers can work individually, in small groups, or use the integrated publishing suite to make contributions to Nucleus Developer Notes that will be publicly available. Currently, access can be requested by sending an email to build@bnext.bio.

3 - Nucleus Developer Notes (devnotes.bnext.bio)

Nucleus Developer Notes is a publishing platform for rapidly sharing new developments with the Nucleus Ecosystem. The Core Development team at b.next integrates work shared as DevNotes into the Nucleus Distribution.

- Developer Notes (DevNotes). DevNotes are the mechanism by which contributions to the Nucleus Distribution are made. DevNotes resemble scientific publications but can be structured like a software project. The scope of a typical DevNote is a single claim. They are built on Jupyter Notebooks, providing integration with data, analysis, and a variety of other file types. They can be issued a DOI, enabling them to be easily found and cited. DevNotes come in a variety of flavors including new modules, proposed work, result replication, negative results, and technical notes. In general, DevNotes are regarded as preprints and not classified as published work.

Making a Contribution

What is a Developer Note (DevNote)?

DevNotes are a short form of scientific communication that can be described in one sentence. They provide the Nucleus community with a means to rapidly share useful results and insights. Since they are built on top of Jupyter Notebooks they can easily integrate code and a variety of file types, bundling an entire research workflow into a discrete package (Figure 2A). DevNotes are used to make contributions to the Nucleus Distribution and can be generated on Nucleus Hub (Figure 2B). Results and insights that are highly useful and/or relevant will be integrated into the Nucleus Distribution by the Core Development Team at b.next.

What can I contribute as a Nucleus Developer Note?

Anything related to PURE-based cytosols and synthetic cells is solidly within the scope of Nucleus. Ideally, contributions should build on existing components of the Nucleus Distribution in some way. There is no limitation on how long or short a DevNote should be. A good rule of thumb is that you should be able to describe your DevNote in one sentence. Some examples might include:

- Experimental plans. Even if you are just planning an experiment, feel free to submit it as a DevNote to let others know how you're thinking about approaching the problem and get feedback from others earlier. DevNotes can be updated so experimental data can be included along the way
- Module development. Experimental data showing that a genetically encoded module works in PURE. The corresponding DevNote should include data, a design file containing sequence information, and a protocol showing how to implement the module.
- Experimental replication. If you're planning to use a component from the existing Nucleus Distribution or from the literature as part of a larger experiment, sharing that the module works in PURE in your hands would be valuable to others.
- Technical Notes. If you have a trick you use for making routine lab work more efficient or more reliable, share it with others.
- Open questions. If there are questions that you feel are worth writing up and of interest to this community, others would probably love to know about them and might even have some answers!

If you're not sure where to start or have an idea for a new type of DevNote and want to get involved, don't hesitate to reach out to build@bnext.bio.

When should I contribute to Nucleus?

The small scale and flexibility of the DevNote format means that they can be shared at any time during the research process that the contributor thinks would be appropriate. DevNotes are considered preprints and therefore do not count as previously published material. DevNotes can be shared along the research journey and be used as building blocks for assembling longer format manuscripts. This strategy would provide a means to organize work while getting credit and feedback along the way.

A)

B)

Developer Note Structure

```

|Developer Note
|_ _build
|_ experiment
|   |_ YYYYMMDD-experiment-name
|   |   |_ 01-general
|   |   |_ 02-design
|   |   |_ 02-data
|   |   |_ 03-analysis
|   |_ YYYYMMDD-experiment-name
|_ figures
|_ src
|_ curvenote.yml
|_ environment.yml
|_ main.md
|_ LICENSE.md
|_ CONTRIBUTING.md
|_ README.md
          
```

Key Nucleus Hub Features

1. Create experimental workflow templates
2. Preview Developer Note
3. Publish Developer Note to Nucleus
4. Access collaborative workspace

Figure 2: Developer Notes and Nucleus Hub. A) Human-readable view of a Nucleus Developer Note; inset shows the underlying file structure. B) View of default landing page for Nucleus Hub; inset shows key user features that work out of the box.

How exactly do I make a contribution?

1. Request Access to Nucleus Hub by navigating to hub.nucleus.engineering and making an account. Email build@bnext.bio to approve your account.
2. Familiarize yourself with the DevNote template by following the guide at nucleus.bnext.bio/devnote-tutorial.
3. Build your project. If your contribution includes experimental components, be sure to structure your project following the template structure. If these don't work for your particular project, let us know!
4. Submit your DevNote to be posted on devnotes.bnext.bio.
5. Questions? Don't hesitate to reach out to build@bnext.bio.

Open Source Licensing

Open source licensing refers to a practice pioneered by the software industry that made it possible to easily share, reuse, and modify software code. Open source licenses provide a clear signal for what others can legally do with contributed software code, reducing barriers to participation and making it straightforward to build on the work of others. This legal clarity has been critical to the success of collaborative software development, enabling software engineers to work together seamlessly across institutional and industry boundaries for decades.

Our goal is to create a similar culture and practice of sharing that enables Nucleus developers to collaborate across institutional and industry boundaries. Nucleus adheres to a permissive open source licensing scheme built on existing, well-established open source licenses appropriate for biotechnology. The Nucleus open source licensing scheme covers more than just software code, it includes protocols, designs, formulations, and materials needed for making synthetic cell modules.

Permissive means that contributions can be used, modified, manufactured, and distributed by anyone for any purpose, including commercial applications.

Nucleus licensing scheme

Table 1: Nucleus contribution component types and corresponding licenses. All contributions are “wrapped” by CERN-OHL-P-2.0.

Component Type	License
Formulations (e.g. cytosol, membrane, etc.), Protocols, Documentation, Jupyter Notebooks, Characterization datasets	CERN-OHL-P-2.0
DNA template designs	CERN-OHL-P-2.0

Biological materials (e.g. plasmids)	CERN-OHL-P-2.0 + OpenMTA
Software (e.g. CDK)	MIT
DevNotes	CC-BY-4.0

What rights and obligations do these licenses provide?

Contributions are licensed under the CERN Open Hardware License-Permissive version 2.0 (CERN-OHL-P-2.0), endorsed by the Open Source Initiative as meeting all requirements for being a true open source license. This permissive license gives users the right to make and convey products manufactured or assembled from the licensed source material. Contributors are encouraged to read and familiarize themselves with all of the licenses used in the Nucleus Ecosystem. This specific license was chosen because it includes provisions directed to the manufacture and assembly of physical products, including non-source code elements, such as designs, and includes terms for both copyright and patents, essential for working with biotechnology contributions. Users are required to acknowledge contributors for their work and retain all notices and acknowledgements. The CERN-OHL-P “wraps” the entire contribution, while individual components of a contribution such as datasets or protocols may also be licensed under a more specific, compatible license as described in Table 1. This is particularly useful if a contribution makes use of existing components that are available under existing, compatible licenses.

When is open source licensing appropriate? Open source licensing is appropriate when you want to allow others to freely use, modify, and distribute one’s own contribution. It’s ideal when you want to encourage community collaboration, build on existing projects, or make your contribution widely accessible.

Contributions that describe foundational or “low-level” capacities are ideally suited for an open source licensing approach. Foundational capacities such as molecular logic or energy generation modules stand to improve the utility of a significant number of other components if made accessible and interoperable. “Low-level” capacities such as basic sensing mechanisms or cellular machinery components are not particularly valuable in isolation; instead they become valuable when used in combination with many other components, most likely developed by third parties.

Contributions that describe capacities that are valuable in isolation may not be well suited for open source licensing. For example, a sensor for a specific therapeutic target or pathway for production of a valuable compound could serve as the basis for a successful company and should be evaluated for commercial viability as proprietary IP. Deployment of a proprietary sensor using an open source Nucleus synthetic cell as a deployment chassis would be possible under the Nucleus open source licensing scheme.

It is always possible to go open source first and take a proprietary approach later. Releasing early, foundational work as open source can benefit others and provide you with valuable feedback. Proprietary applications can be built on top of the open foundation and benefit from community improvements to the underlying platform.

How do I make an open source contribution?

The structure of Nucleus DevNotes makes it straightforward to release your contribution into the core open source distribution:

1. Read the license.txt file contained in the root directory of the DevNote template
2. Declare which files are considered Covered Source in the license.txt file. The default declaration should cover most use cases.
3. Submit the DevNote. By submitting the DevNote you acknowledge that you have the rights to license others to use your work.

Questions?

For guidance on licensing decisions or help implementing these practices, contact us at build@bnext.bio

APPENDIX 2:

Study Interview Guide: researchers

Project: ‘Strengthening Open Science in Synthetic Biology: deriving Open Science Principles for b.next from key stakeholders: a qualitative research study’

Please note that question probes or follow-ups are denoted with bullet points

Demographic and contextual questions:

To begin, I would like to ask you a few questions about yourself:

1) First, what is your job title/position?

- Clinician-scientist
- Institutional technology transfer office representative
- Professor
- Research Associate
- Post-Doctoral researcher
- Graduate Student
- Research Manager

2) Could you please briefly describe the kind of lab you work in?

- Bottom up syn cell
- Top down syn cell
- Cellular engineer
- Cell free and synthetic biology
- Other

3) How many years have you been in practice?

- a) Less than 1 year
- b) 1 to 5 years
- c) 6 to 10 years
- d) 11 to 20 years
- e) More than 20 years

On Open Science in the field of synthetic biology

4) In your view, what are Open Science and Open Source? Are they different? What does working in the ‘open’ mean to you?

- How well do you think Open Science/Open Source are functioning in your field?
- How important are these for advancing the field and benefitting society?

Openness, sharing and collaboration practice

- 5). What does collaboration mean to you and how important is this in your practice?
- How do you feel that open sharing/Open Science relates to collaboration?
 - What is the typical size and form of your research collaborations (if any)?
 - What barriers and challenges have you experienced around your collaborations efforts and what were the outcomes?
 - To what extent would more collaboration be beneficial to your practice?
- 6). Have you had any experience publicly sharing data, research materials or software through open source repositories or in other ways? What was the context? What was the outcome?
- What motivated your participation?
 - Which are your sharing channels of choice? Why?
 - For example, depositing materials on Addgene, sharing datasets on Zenodo, posting manuscripts on open access preprint servers?
 - What problems or challenges did you experience or anticipate?
 - What were the benefits or harms if any, to the research process and results?
 - How did public sharing/ participating in Open Science affect collaboration in your practice?
 - What challenges or benefits do you foresee in obtaining proper attribution or reward for and recognition of your shared work product? How could these challenges best be addressed?
 - Are there considerations around the financial sustainability of open sharing? If so, what are the issues and how do you think they could be resolved?
 - How have your institutional technology transfer office policies affected your participation in open sharing or other open source research hubs? If they have hindered participation is there a way to get around this?
 - How could sharing, collaboration and 'working in the open' be incentivized for institutions?
 - If a trainee would like to work in the 'open' but their Principal Investigator or supervisor does not, is there a way to get around this?

Openness, sharing and collaboration in the context of the Nucleus collaboration platform

7). I am hoping that you had a chance to look over and reflect on the Nucleus White Paper that we sent out with this interview guide. Have you already had experience engaging with Nucleus online or based on the White Paper or your prior knowledge of the Nucleus Ecosystem do you plan to utilize Nucleus' offerings in the future ('Distribution' knowledge resources, 'Hub' collaboration platform or 'DevNotes' knowledge sharing)?

- Which offerings are appealing and why? Are there any you would not choose to participate in and why?
- How does Nucleus relate to other open source hubs? What could be done to maximize the benefits of contributing through Nucleus?
 - Nucleus uses a permissive open source licensing scheme building on existing and well-established open source licenses that are appropriate for biotechnology (CERN-OHL-P-2.0; CC-BY-4.0; MIT; and Open MTA). Do these seem fit-for-purpose to you or are there other supports, arrangements or licenses that would facilitate or otherwise encourage you to more freely share data, samples, software, materials, know-how or insights through DevNotes etc.?
 - Is there anything you would add that would further inspire trust and optimize your participation in Nucleus?
 - Do you have suggestions for a governance structure that could further build community trust in Nucleus?
- How do you think the quality of contributions to Nucleus should be maintained?
- What are your thoughts around ensuring bio-safety with respect to the Nucleus hub?

8). What do you consider to be the appropriate boundaries of Open Science in the field of synthetic biology? Why?

- What scientific resources are you/would you be comfortable sharing and under what circumstances? With what limitations or caveats? Why?
 - Are different conditions required for different kinds of data or scientific resources? For example: Primary and processed datasets and associated meta data; failed or negative experimental data. Scientific tools/materials: experimental protocols, reagents, cell-lines, primers/genetic sequences, antibodies, cell extracts etc.
- At which stage of the research process would it be appropriate to share these items? (eg. immediately upon collection, after processing, after manuscript submission, upon first publication?). What factors inform your answer?
- What are the attributes of projects that are appropriate to work on in the 'open'. Under what circumstances would you avoid working in the 'open'?
- What are your thoughts about a scenario where Nucleus users would work in a 'semi-open' environment where resources are shared only with a 'closed' smaller group of trusted members?

9). Have you had any experiences with patents or other intellectual property rights (IPRs) held by others which affected your research? Have you had any experiences patenting (or asserting other IPRs) over your discoveries? Have you ever sought or do you anticipate asserting protections over discoveries, products or services you might derive from open resources (for example from Nucleus)?

- What motivated you to seek IP protection or to use materials or processes subject to IP protection?

- Have you experienced or do you anticipate problems or challenges around the use of IPRs in the synthetic biology field?
- Conversely, what are the benefits to the research process and results?
- Under what circumstances would it be appropriate to forgo/avoid intellectual property protection (like patents)? Under what circumstances would you consider IPRs important to seek? Why?
- Should contributors be able to share patented materials through Nucleus? If so, how do you see this working?
- What do you think is the best way to manage patenting or 'productization' of entities derived from open resources by users? For example should there be recognition or royalties from any profits fed back to the contributor of the base resource or profits fed back into the Nucleus Ecosystem to benefit the community?
- b.next is planning to sell a formulation of the PURE cell-free expression system that corresponds with the open source formulations they are making available through their open source platform. How do you think Nucleus participants would feel if improvements to PURE developed by users and contributed back to the hub were included in the marketed PURE product? How could this be handled fairly?
- What could be done to optimize the experience of users of Nucleus resources?

10). How could the involvement of firms and industry as contributors or users of the Nucleus Ecosystem best be handled?

- What are the advantages and disadvantages of industry participation in the Nucleus Ecosystem?
- Should industry operate under the same set of requirements and expectations as academic users and contributors? If not, then what scenarios would be preferable?
- How could industry participation be optimized in a way that benefits all of the Nucleus community?
- How could Nucleus best motivate involvement of industry in the Ecosystem?

11). Imagine there was a physical lab space to support the collaborative development of synthetic cells. For example, it could host 'Research Fellows' who may wish to move projects and discoveries between a Nucleus lab and their home institutional laboratories. How might this best work?

- How could bringing existing knowledge to the Nucleus labs be managed? Could fellows bring an IP protected entity to work on at Nucleus?
- How could management of new discoveries made at Nucleus Labs best function? For example, could a Fellow seek to patent and commercialize something they develop while at Nucleus? Equally, how do you see subsequent collaboration and publication working?

12). What do you see as the relationship or what should be the boundary between Nucleus and b.next?

Broader research and innovation ecosystem

13). In your view how well functioning is the research and innovation ecosystem in your country? If there are problems or barriers what are they? What solutions might work best? Could greater openness assist with improving these issues? How could the Nucleus Ecosystem or b.next as a developer and producer of reagents and tools assist? For example, could Nucleus help with mediating more effective interactions between industry and academia?

Please consider from the perspective of:

- Commercialization pathways
- Funding
- Reward and attribution
- Publishing
- Social and environmental justice

Key priorities and additional factors

14). In your view, having reflected on the policy and practice outlined in the Nucleus White Paper, does this seem fit-for-purpose in facilitating collaboration, discovery and innovation in the synthetic cell field? Are there any key elements you would add or change?

- Are there any issues we haven't yet discussed that could make Open Science in synthetic biology or Nucleus function better or anything else you would like to mention?

Thank you for participating!

APPENDIX 3:

Study Interview Guide: Technology transfer professionals

Project: ‘Strengthening Open Science in Synthetic Biology: deriving Open Science Principles for b.next from key stakeholders: a qualitative research study’

Thank you for taking the time to speak with us today. This study aims to understand how we can best bootstrap the synthetic cell and biology innovation ecosystem by deploying an open source collaborative platform Nucleus, recently launched by b.next corp. out of San Francisco. Greater openness through open source and open science approaches to dissemination of research outputs is one avenue aiming to accelerate discovery and translation to impact. So far in this study we have interviewed researchers working in academic, not-for-profit and governmental settings asking them about their interest and experience working with open source projects – in particular Nucleus. Many spoke about the definitive role that TTOs play in how researchers are able to transfer their technologies to the world. We would like to ask you about your knowledge, experience and perspectives on open source approaches, particularly in the biology/ biotech space.

Please note that question probes or follow-ups are denoted with bullet points.

Demographic and contextual questions:

To begin, I would like to ask you a few quick questions about yourself:

- 1) First, what is your job title/position and academic background?
- 2) How many years have you been in practice?

On TTOs, open source and open science:

- 3) Could you please tell us about the mandate and key goals of your institutional technology transfer office?
 - Dissemination of knowledge; securing new sources of revenue for the institution through commercialization; ensuring researchers’ outputs are not misused or exploited; raising the profile of the institution and its researchers to attract funding, collaborations and donations etc.?
- 4) What do you see as the elements of a highly successful handling/dissemination/translation of a research artifact from the view of your TTO?
 - How do you measure the success of such a technology transfer?

- How successful do you consider current efforts to be?
- Do most outputs that are patented end up being licensed?
- Who do you see as the most important stakeholders in your endeavour and why?

5) Open science and open source are becoming better known as ways to more rapidly share knowledge, accelerate discovery and innovation, allow for better replication and less duplication of research, and improve the economy of the scientific endeavour. This may also translate into quicker and more cost-effective options for public access when a product is developed. As well, open options offer an alternative business model that in some technology areas may be best suited to energize innovation. How is the awareness of open source and open science in your place of work and in your profession more broadly?

- How do you see the difference between open source and open science?
- Do you find there is greater awareness of open approaches in recent times? How so? And if not why not?
- What is your understanding of how greater openness (open source and open science) could work for your institution? What do you see as the opportunities or risks?
- Can you see benefits for your stakeholders through the use of open source and open science avenues to tech transfer?
- How do you regard open source software contributions – how have they challenged or changed existing tech transfer practices? Do your institution and researchers always follow established policy and practice in (open source) software transfer or is there a discrepancy?
- Most examples may be in realm of software but please tell us about any open source biotechnology projects you have encountered? How did you navigate technology transfer? What are key points of difference between the software and the biotech paradigms? Are there transferable lessons learned?
- Please tell us about any open source or open science avenues you may offer to researchers or that you support them in pursuing? Eg. use of the Open MTA, permissive licenses such as the CERN-OHL-P-2.0 or Apache v2, commercialization in the absence of patents/open source business models, sharing to open repositories, placing inventions in the public domain etc.
- How do you help researchers decide what is the best approach to take in handling their outputs?
- Do you have public health, ethics or public benefit concessions in your technology transfer framework? Could you see these be deployed in navigating open source avenues?
- What are the key barriers to greater deployment of open source avenues?
- How do the requirements of the Bayh-Dole Act segue with open science and open source approaches?

- 6) How does your office set its priorities and goals? How responsive are these to changes in the research and innovation landscape (government policy; funder requirements; what other institutions are doing; shifting cultural, societal or ethical norms and citizen expectations?).
- Have these goals and priorities shifted in response to there being an increase in open source projects?
 - What incentives or different metrics could be deployed to encourage greater openness in technology transfer?
 - Are open source approaches considered a viable tech transfer mechanism and if not, what kind of examples or demonstrations would be considered convincing?
- 7) Have you come across Nucleus – an open source platform to enable the collaborative development of synthetic cells. We have also sent you a White Paper detailing the project which we hope you had a chance to take a quick look at.
- Do you have any feedback about this open source model?
 - How comfortable would your office be in allowing researchers to contribute research outputs to the Nucleus repository?
 - How comfortable would your office be in releasing patented research artifacts to Nucleus under a permissive license such as the CERN-OHL-P-2.0 or the Apache v2 that grant royalty-free, non-exclusive license to use the patented material to licensees? If you are not comfortable with such licenses what would be the key objections?
- 8) Does your institution take measures to educate or highlight the concept of greater openness to researchers?
- Is your institution interested in knowing more about how greater openness could work for you and your community?
 - What do you see as the best way to generate this knowledge or get this education? What is needed or who needs to bring their expertise?
 - Some institutions have founded 'Open Source Program Offices' (OSPOs). What are your thoughts on these?
 - What is the role of researcher funders and foundations in encouraging open science at your institutions and more broadly?
- 9) Are there any issues we haven't yet discussed that could make open science in synthetic biology or Nucleus function better or anything else you would like to mention?

Thank you very much for participating!

APPENDIX 4:

Additional details regarding collection of demographic data from interviewees

The first part of the interview collected demographic information. Where required and possible, these data were verified through internet searches. The information included: researcher field of practice (self-identified from a list we compiled and verified by b.next as meaningful) or TTO professional; years of research experience post-PhD; gender; job title; region and country of institution. Time in practice was recorded in one of four categories: trainee, <10; 10 - 20; 20 - 30 and 30+ years. Job title included PIs, group leaders, trainees or TTO professionals. Research field included: bottom-up synthetic cell; cellular engineering; synthetic biology and cell-free; and top-down (and middle-out) synthetic cell research. Demographics were used to examine if opinions and practice varied between groups.

APPENDIX 5:

CODING AND ANALYTICAL CATEGORIES

Substantive themes:

1) Opinions on patenting

- Concerns or drawbacks of patenting
- Positive effects or advantages of patenting
- Researchers' opinions and choices around patenting
- Alternative pathways to impact beyond patents

2) Collaboration

- Collaboration is critical to researcher practice
- Importance of licenses, agreements and NDAs
- Importance of personal connections for building trust
- Importance of funding or shared funding
- Importance of shared goals
- Types of collaboration
- What collaboration involves

3) Cultural or attitude aspects of openness and closed-ness

- Differing attitude to patenting in the US vs EU
- Comparisons between software and biotech Open Source
- Importance of responsible and ethical synthetic biologists
- Need for a cultural change to optimize sharing
- Research or institution leader or PI sets sharing culture
- Synthetic cell research and sharing culture

4) Current sharing practice

- Definitions or understandings of open science and open source
- Does not participate in open sharing beyond std publication
- Does not share data
- Does not use the OpenMTA
- Has not patented anything
- Methods/protocols easier to share
- Researcher has patents or preparing/in progress
- Researcher side-stepping TTO to patent individually
- Researcher side-stepping TTO to share or access
- The default is to make things public – 'we share almost everything'
- The default is to patent
- Timing of sharing (after publication/pre-print; after internal review process; before publication)

- Ways to share (Addgene; pre-print or Bioarchiv; Github; NCBI; never done a pre-print; has not ever shared to Addgene; NCBI; open repositories inc. Protocols.io, Zenodo); standard publication; to labs directly on request)
- Would not share commercially valuable outputs (including to Nucleus)

5) Disincentives or challenges to sharing or open science

- Biosafety concerns
- Potential for mis-use of shared materials/knowledge
- Cost and logistics etc. challenges of sharing materials to distant locations
- Ensuring what is shared is meaningful, useful and validated
- In-person sharing is needed for optimal knowledge transfer
- MTAs and legal agreements
- National security concerns
- Need for staff to manage sharing
- Others may not reciprocate/ free-loaders
- Researcher time and money invested in resource creation
- Tension between open sharing and patenting
- Time and cost burden of sharing outputs
- Concerns about protecting competitive advantage
- Concerns about scooping
- Discomfort about breaking new ground to openly share

6) Incentives and advantages to open science

- Importance of incentives to make sharing worth it
- Importance of a shared framework or set of expectations
- Incentives for institutions to participate in OS
- Motivations to share or go open
 - o Academic credit and DOIs
 - o Academic or ethical sharing ethos
 - o Importance of sharing negative results
 - o Improving scientific reproducibility, dissemination and impact
 - o Increased prestige visibility and professional reward
 - o Metrics for open science
 - o More collaborations, community and connections
 - o Personal reasons for doing open work
 - o Sharing during research process can improve outcomes
 - o Sharing mandated by funder
 - o Sharing to repository for efficiency

7) Concerns and opinions about b.next and their activities (to be reported in a future publication)

- Researchers' relationship or history with b.next and use of Nucleus
- Positive sentiment toward Nucleus/b.next
- Perceived problems with Nucleus/b.next
- Limited understanding or familiarity with b.next/Nucleus
- Concerns about b.next being for-profit
- Attitude to patenting of derivatives of shared resources (permissive/ negative)
- Commercial entities will take advantage of openness
- DevNotes
- Fellows or students visiting b.next
- Needs to attain critical mass
- Industry involvement in Nucleus

8) Requirements to encourage participation in Nucleus (to be reported in a future publication)

- Building trust and encouraging participation
 - o Importance of a governance structure
 - o Importance of transparency and clear rules of engagement
- How b.next could give back or be profitable
 - o b.next potential commercialization plan
 - o benefit-sharing from commercialization
- Roles for b.next in improving the R&I system
 - o Developing case studies and evidence around OS pathways
 - o Education for TTOs and researchers around risks and benefits of OS pathways
 - o In lab training modules for researchers
 - o Instil system of meaningful metrics to encourage openness
 - o Platform for discussion of IP and OS pathways to impact
 - o Prize or competition incentive
 - o Prototyping new model and changing the culture
 - o Quarterback multi-disciplinary conversation around OS pathways
 - o Raising the profile of syn cell research and its promise
 - o Quarterback setting of standards and the maintenance and QC of reagents and materials
 - o Start-up support for syn cells
 - o Research funding and student fellowships
 - o Supplier or syn cells or PURE
 - o Support of Build-a-Cell

9) Opinions about the current research and innovation system

- Govt and funder policy for OS is supportive (UK)
- Growing interest in alternative funding beyond public grants
- Growing interest in academic-industry partnership
- Innovation and commercialization is working well (US)

- Narrow focus on patents as the only path to impact
- Reproducibility of science concerns
- Research funding challenges
- Uncertainty about the productization of syn cells
- VC or start-up challenges

10) Societal or scientific challenges for the synthetic cell field

- Importance of societal engagement with syn cells and their promise
- Integration and standards problem
- Lack of connectivity and coordination between researchers
- Need for deep intellectual inquiry into what is meaningful to measure
- Scientific challenges

11) TTO Policy and practice

- Goals, stakeholders and measures of success
 - o Metrics for impact and success
 - o Stakeholders for TTO practice and outcomes
 - o TTO role is to capture the value of researchers work
 - o TTOs offering start-up support
- Implications of Bayh-Dole for OS
 - o Federal funding should not go to directly benefit for-profit companies
- Licensing strategies and differential access
 - o Academic vs commercial licensing
 - o Diligence licensing for the public good
 - o Non-exclusive licensing
 - o Public domain licenses
- TTO miscellaneous stats and history
- TTO policy and practice around patenting and MTAs
 - o Ownership of IP made by researchers
 - o TTOs are there to partner and assist researchers
 - o Differing attitude toward patenting across TTOs
 - o TTOs patent pre-emptively without a licensee lined up
 - o TTOs are selective about what they will patent
 - o TTOs more stringent with material transfers
- TTOs understanding and acceptance of Open Source
 - o TTO discomfort with open source licensing and the Open MTA
 - o TTO acceptance or understanding of Open Source and open science

Auxiliary themes:

1) Companies and policy

- Lack of commercial companies in syn cell field
- Open source companies or non-profits
- Opinions on the kinds of technology patentable in syn cell field
- Policy or funders mentioned
- Syn cell companies

2) Miscellaneous background and demographics

- Fields of research, labs, research organisms, meetings and projects
 - o Organisms and labs
 - Artificial human chromosome labs
 - Clostridium
 - E.coli
 - Mycoplasma
 - Yeast
 - o Organizations and meetings
 - Align Foundation
 - Bio-Bricks
 - Build-a-Cell
 - Fab Lab
 - Free Genes
 - Gathering for Open Science Hardware (GOSH)
 - Genetech
 - iGEM
 - JCVI – Venter Institute
 - NIST
 - Open Plant
 - PURE cytosol workshop
 - reClone
 - Stanford
 - Synthetic Genomics
 - Twist gene synthesis
 - o Researcher fields of practice
 - Bottom up syn cells
 - Cellular engineering
 - Synthetic biology and cell-free
 - Top down syn cells
 - o Misc people, tech and projects
 - Drew Endy
 - Gibson assembly
 - Liberty Cell
 - Minimal cell
 - Mirror life

- Other sharing platforms for specific organisms
- Professional position of participant
- Researcher background
- Time in practice

3) NVivo codes and interesting quotes

- Free riders are part of the scenario
- I wouldn't begrudge them making money
- Pragmatic openness
- Sharing kills your IP
- Slow science is good science
- We IP everything

4) Suggestions for additional interviewees

5) Value/ interest in this b.next study